

SYNTHESIS OF DIHYDROXYTARTRONIC ACID

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A synthesis of dihydroxytartaric acid has been described

As a preliminary to the synthesis of ascorbic acid (I), the dihydroxytartronic acid (II) has been synthesised according to the method described below.

Magnesium-(or better the sodio) salt of acetoxy malonic ester in benzene is reacted in the cold with chloroacetyl chloride; the resulting condensation product, chloroacetyl-acetoxy malonic ester on hydrolysis under specific conditions yields the lactone (II), m.p. 153° (decomp.) (literature 153°, Michael and Jung, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1291).

Further investigations in this line are in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl Acetoxy malonate.—Ethyl bromomalonate (45 g.) was reacted with freshly fused potassium acetate (22 g.) under glacial acetic acid by refluxing gently in an oil-bath for 4 hours. The reaction product was treated with excess of cold water and worked up according to the usual procedure, yield 31 g.

The use of sodium acetate in place of potassium acetate resulted in very poor yield.

Ethyl Chloroacetylacetoxy malonate.—(a) The magnesium-salt of ethyl acetoxy malonate was condensed with chloroacetyl chloride according to the following method (*cf.* Lund, *Ber.*, 1934, 67 935).

Ethyl acetoxy malonate (11 g.), magnesium (1.2 g.), alcohol (5 c.c.) and a few drops of carbon tetrachloride were taken in a flask fitted with a condenser and guard tubes and refluxed on a water-bath. When the reaction started, a mixture of ethyl acetoxy malonate (11 g.) and alcohol (8 c.c.) was dropped from a dropping funnel and the refluxing was continued till the whole of magnesium went into solution. The flask was then cooled, 50 c.c. of dry ether were added and then a mixture of 15 g.

of chloroacetyl chloride and 20 c.c. of ether dropped. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water bath for 2 hours. On cooling it was treated with excess of cold water containing a little sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, ether removed and distilled. The fraction boiling at $145-50^{\circ}/10$ mm. was collected, yield 10 g. (Found : C, 44.7 ; H, 5.07 ; Cl, 11.8. $C_{11}H_{15}O_7Cl$ requires C, 44.8 ; 5.09 ; Cl, 12.1 per cent).

(b) Ethyl acetoxy malonate (6.1g.) was dropped slowly on molecularised sodium (0.8 g.) under benzene in a flask cooled in ice and the flask was kept overnight when all the sodium went into solution. The sodio-salt of ethyl acetoxy malonate in benzene was next dropped on 5 g. of chloroacetyl chloride in the cold and the reaction mixture after 5-6 hours was refluxed for 2-3 hours on a water-bath and then worked up as usual and distilled, the fraction boiling at $145-50^{\circ}/10$ mm. being collected, yield 5 g.

Dihydroxytartronic Acid (II).—The hydrolysis of ethyl chloroacetylacetoxy malonate to dihydroxytartronic acid was repeatedly attempted according to the method of Anschütz and Bertram (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 471), but all efforts proved to be unsuccessful. Finally, it was hydrolysed as follows :

Sodium (1.6 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (25 c.c.), 1.5 c.c. of water (calculated to form sodium hydroxide with sodium) was added and nitrogen was bubbled through the mixture. After some time, when the air had been replaced by nitrogen, 5 g. of the condensation product were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 hours. Salts, which separated on cooling, were filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dissolved in water freed from air by boiling and cooling in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and kept overnight in nitrogen atmosphere. The solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly (10 times) extracted with ethyl acetate. Ethyl acetate was removed and the residue kept in a vacuum desiccator, when clusters of needle-shaped crystals were obtained which on recrystallisation from ether melted at 153° (decomp.). (Found ; C, 41.2 ; H, 3.45. Calc. for $C_4H_4O_4$: C, 41.4 ; H, 3.45 per cent).

The use of water in excess of the calculated amount resulted in the failure of the reaction.

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